

A didactic low-cost neural network prototype for industrial parts classification

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ABSTRACT

Pattern recognition techniques are increasingly used in industrial applications, such as identifying defects in industrial parts to ensure the quality of the final product. Mastering such techniques is now mandatory in the training of many professionals in the technology field. This work aimed to use these techniques to develop a low-cost classifier for parts based on the Perceptron Multilayer (MLP) neural network using the physical characteristics of their color and length. The network was trained with hundreds of samples collected using a didactic prototype system and color and length sensors controlled by an Arduino. The data from the trained network was fed into an application that, when classifying each piece, received the sensor readings in real time and displayed a visual representation of the identified class. The classifier achieved a hit rate of 81.6%, which is significant given that this was a low-cost prototype using only two features of the objects extracted by sensors that were highly susceptible to external interference. Its integration into classroom settings, especially in the context of Industry 4.0, can provide students with hands-on experience in dealing with real-world challenges.

Keywords: Supervised learning, multilayer perceptron, didactic prototype, low-cost.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ensuring that a product meets the specified technical requirements is of fundamental importance when controlling the production stages, impacting manufacturing costs, process safety, the quality of the end product, and the satisfaction of the customer for whom the result is intended.

It is increasingly common to use pattern recognition techniques in industrial applications to identify characteristics of parts. However, in many cases, defect analysis procedures are still performed in a non-optimal way, either due to the object's complexity or limited access to an automated system that performs this task with the necessary accuracy.

The process of identifying the physical characteristics of an object is an essential procedure for an automated system to be able to identify defects in industrial parts in Industry 4.0. Numerous alternatives exist for acquiring data to extract information about an object's characteristics. However, from the use of camera images to simpler sensors, a common factor among all solutions is the need to process the data collected to make it possible to recognize the desired patterns.

To approximate the challenges of this industry to academia, didactic prototypes can be used, as indicated by Pajpach et al. (2022). Besides that, didactic prototypes promote experimental learning. As shown in Freitas and Fortes, 2020, practical activities are essential to effective learning, according to the students. Also, mastering pattern recognition techniques is now mandatory in the training of many professionals in the technology field.

Thus, we present a didactic low-cost neural network prototype. We implement a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) to identify the characteristics of a batch of parts and classify them according to pre-established parameters based on physical characteristics: color and length. This prototype can be used in the classroom to stimulate creativity and neural network learning based on hands-on experience for the students.

2 BACKGROUND

In supervised learning, the classes are defined according to the designer's needs, and the system adapts to these features in unsupervised clustering. However, the number of classes can generally be determined, and the system is responsible for specifying the characteristics that define a group or not.

Bearing that the characteristics of the items to be classified are well-defined, and we want to know if the item being evaluated is following known parameters, this work aims to apply a supervised pattern recognition strategy to perform this task.

Silva (2010) states that pattern recognition comprises three main phases: in the first stage data on the classified item is obtained from the sensors; in the next stage this

data is processed by the system to extract the characteristics read; and finally, in the last stage, the decision is made (ranking).

Among the various possibilities for implementing pattern recognition algorithms, the use of artificial intelligence techniques such as artificial neural networks should be highlighted. According to Mueller (1996): "Artificial neural networks are based on studies of the structure of the human brain to try to emulate its intelligent way of processing information."

Neural networks can have different architectural models, which differ according to the arrangement of the neurons in their structure. Matich (2001) describes the fundamental parameters of a neural network as being the number of layers, the number of neurons per layer, the degree of connectivity, and the type of connections between the neurons.

A multilayer perceptron (MLP) is a neural network configuration in which the neurons are arranged in an input layer, an output layer and intermediate layers called hidden layers. Unlike the simple Perceptron, the MLP network can contain several neurons both in the input layer and the intermediate layers, as well as in the output layer. Figure 1 shows the structure of a MLP network with four layers.

The MLP network is one of the most versatile neural network configurations, used in pattern recognition and function approximation, time series prediction, and system optimization applications (Silva et al., 2017). MLPs can be used to approximate any continuous function and can solve problems such as classify samples present in non-linearly separable data sets (Abirami & Chitra, 2020), which broadens the algorithm's applicability to the pattern recognition task.

Figure 1 - Structure of a MLP network with four layers where, X_j is an input feature, W_{ji} is the weight between neurons, I_j is an input vector and Y_j is an output vector.

The MLP network's learning process is based on the backpropagation algorithm. The process of executing this algorithm is divided into two phases, the first called forward and the second called backward.

The MLP network training process consists of successively executing the phases of the backpropagation algorithm, comparing the results obtained with those desired until a certain stopping criterion is reached. This stopping criterion is usually related to the level of error between the samples analyzed and the answers obtained in the network's output, but it is also common for a maximum number of iterations to be considered as a limit for running the algorithm.

The applicability of MLP is diverse, covering different areas of knowledge as engineering and healthcare. For example, in the work of Sanzana et al. (2023) the authors use MLP to predict the water volume that needs to be chilled in a Thermal-Energy-Storage-Air-Conditioning system. In Singhal & Sharma (2023) the authors discuss the possibility of diagnosis of diseases such as Parkinson and Asthma as well as the identification of gender, age, and emotions by extracting features from the voice signal of the speaker and analyzing it using AI such as the MLP.

3 METHODOLOGY

The system developed aims to correctly classify the parts presented using a MLP network. We used a simple part to represent an industrial part: plastic building blocks of different colors and sizes.

We developed a didactic prototype of a conveyor belt system controlled by an Arduino. We use a color sensor consisting of a TAOS TCS3200 chip, capable of measuring and detecting a wide range of visible colors, converting a light signal into a frequency signal that a microcontroller can read, and four white LEDs, used to illuminate the object being analyzed. The device works by reading a matrix of photodiodes made up of 8 rows and 8 columns divided as follows: sixteen photodiodes with a red filter, sixteen photodiodes with a green filter, sixteen photodiodes with a blue filter, and sixteen photodiodes without a filter.

Another essential component was the barrier sensor composed of an LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) and a laser diode. Its function is to identify the presence of the part so that the color sensor can read it. With it, it is also possible to analyze the time it takes for a part to completely cross the light beam to obtain a reading corresponding to the length of the part.

The didactic prototype was previously designed on a computer and then built using low-cost materials. The belt was cut from vinyl canvas, and the movement was provided by a 5V motor coupled to a Tamiya model 70168 gearbox. Control of the motor and reading of the sensors was carried out by an Arduino Mega 2560, which, in the training stage, records the sensor measurements on an SD card and, in the classification stage, communicates this data directly to the application developed for the computer.

The part to be classified must be positioned on a conveyor belt system, which collects the color and length data of the parts and transmits it to a computer that performs the classification process in real-time using the neural network and an application developed to visualize the classification obtained.

For this task to be possible, the network must be trained beforehand using MATLAB software, in which the MLP algorithm was implemented.

At this stage, six different parts were positioned on the conveyor belt, one by one, repeatedly, at random. Their measurements were collected by the color and length sensors and stored on the SD card in a CSV format file. An Ethernet module for Arduino was

used only to record the data on the SD card, as it was already available. For the training 300 samples were collected.

The measurements recorded on the SD card were then transferred to the computer, where the network would be trained. The dataset was previously normalized using the Z score method and constituted three color measurements (red, green, and blue) and one length measurement, used as the network's input. The algorithm was developed in such a way as to be able to run an MLP network with any number of inputs, layers and neurons, allowing tests to be carried out in an agile and diverse manner.

The training algorithm receives as input parameters a vector with the network dimensions (topology), a matrix with the normalized measurements for each sample, a matrix with the known classification of each sample, the learning rate, and the stopping criteria, which are both the minimum desired error and the maximum number of iterations (which occurs first). As output, the function generates matrices with the synaptic weights, a vector with the evolution of the error in each iteration, and the total training time.

The network topology was defined using the cross-validation method. Here, the aim is to analyze the performance of each candidate topology when the network is applied to a different set of samples from the one used during the training stage (Silva et al., 2016). The total number of samples collected is randomly divided into two sets: the first, the training set, which is used to train the network, and the second, the validation set, which is responsible for evaluating the performance of the trained network. The training and validation sets comprised 60% and 40% of the samples, respectively, with 300 samples collected for this stage.

Tests with different network topologies were carried out and based on the hit rates of the topologies tested, it was decided to use a network with three layers: the input layer with 4 neurons, the hidden layer with 14 neurons, and the output layer with 6 neurons. It should be noted that the size of the output layer was previously defined as the number of classes in which the pieces were to be classified. The size of the input layer is related to the number of input features measured by the sensors (RGB data and length).

The network's overall performance was measured in each iteration by the Mean Square Error (MSE) function, and the maximum number of iterations was set at 10000.

The learning rate is a parameter that determines how quickly the network learns and is usually represented by a value between 0.1 and 1. A low value for the learning rate

will cause the network to take longer to converge, while a very high value for this parameter can cause the network to oscillate and not stabilize at an acceptable value.

Tests were conducted with learning rates of 0.1, 0.5 and 1. Compared to the other rates, as expected, the learning rate of 0.1 was the one that resulted in the longest training time (757.19 seconds) and the highest number of iterations (4474), but these factors are not decisive given the objectives of this work. In the training sessions, the maximum number of iterations was not reached, and training stopped using the minimum error criterion. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the MSE with the iterations for the learning rate of 0.1. In this test, the network achieved a success rate of 93%.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

4 RESULTS

The developed didactic prototype is shown in Figure 3. In turn, Figure 4 shows the sensors used and the area on the conveyor belt where the parts pass through before being identified. Through this prototype, we collected data to compose a dataset to train our MPL neural network, allowing the parts classification in real-time.

Figure 3. The developed prototype (controlled conveyor belt and sensors).

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Figure 4. Detail of the sensors on the developed prototype (a) Color sensor and four LEDs, (b) Barrier sensor receiver and (c) Barrier sensor emitter.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The data obtained from training the network was supplied to the application developed to display the results of the classified parts in real time. Figure 5 shows the Development Interface (IDE) application developed in the Delphi language. This IDE allows the use of the Rapid Application Development (RAD) concept, a development model that prioritizes the rapid creation of prototypes.

In the initial test, 20 samples of each class were randomly inserted into the treadmill, for a total of 120 samples. The ambient lighting, which varied throughout the day, and problems in stabilizing the speed of the treadmill, represented external disturbances in the measurements provided by the sensors, which were not circumvented by the network's generalization capacity, resulting in many classification errors.

Figure 5. Interface application developed showing the classification of a part: small and pink.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The aforementioned problems were solved by adding a cover over the reading area of the color sensor and fixing the power cable of the treadmill motor, which was apparently the cause of the speed variations (interfering in the length measurement of the parts).

Once the network parameters have been defined, the network validation process was carried out using only the forward step of the MLP algorithm. A new set of 300 samples was collected (50 for each part) and divided into 60% for training and 40% for validation. The network obtained correctly classified 92.3% of the samples and was selected for real-time classification using the application developed for this purpose.

Once again, the data from the trained network was fed into the application and a new battery of tests was carried out with twenty parts of each class (total of 120 parts) randomly placed on the conveyor belt for real-time classification. The hit rate was 81.6%, which we considered a satisfactory result given that this was a low-cost prototype that used only two characteristics of the object, extracted by sensors that were highly susceptible to external interference.

We believe that this hit rate can be increased with improvements in the physical part of the project, especially with regard to the conveyor belt, a mechanism with extreme importance both in the data collection stage for training and in the data reading stage for classification.

5 CONCLUSION

This work presented a classifier based on the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) neural network developed for parts classification. For that, a low-cost prototype was developed based on the information of color and barrier sensors. The network was trained with hundreds of samples acquired directly from the sensors and the result of the classification were shown in an interface application.

Even using this small dataset, the classifier obtained an accuracy of 81.6%. The results can be considered satisfactory, given the low-cost prototype and the existence of possible undetected interferences. In future works, we pretend to include redundancies for the color and length sensors, extract new features using other sensors, increase the dataset and test other pattern recognition techniques with the system. Another possible improvement is capturing images of objects through cameras, which can analyze two-dimensional data of the parts, in addition to the colors.

Improvements can also be implemented in the MLP neural network training code, such as the inclusion of the momentum term, preventing the training from converging to a local minimum; use of adaptive learning rate, improving network convergence time; simultaneous comparison of the success rate in the test group and the validation group during training, making it possible to verify the beginning of the overfitting problem, which, when detected, can act as a stopping criterion replacing the minimum error parameter; and also the use of confusion matrices, allowing the analysis of the classifier's performance in each of the proposed classes.

Beyond its technical accomplishments, the didactic nature of the prototype presents a valuable opportunity for educational integration. The study suggests that the prototype, emphasizing practical problem-solving in Industry 4.0, can be valuable in classroom settings. This prototype can provide hands-on experience to students in a creative way involving real-world challenges.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data and scripts that support this work are available at:
<https://www.monografias.ufop.br/handle/35400000/1763>

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